

INVESTIGATION ON THE ROLE OF UNSTEADY AERODYNAMICS IN 1F FLUTTER OF WIDE CHORD TRANSONIC FAN BLADES

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ABSTRACT

The paper investigates flutter of the 1F mode on wide chord fan blades at high working lines and seeks to understand the root cause mechanism by which unsteady blade aerodynamics leads to negative aerodamping. 9 blades have been predicted with a 3D URANS CFD code at a range of operating points, which are then each analysed at 5 radial sections to understand what causes aerodamping of an aerofoil to be either positive or negative. It is found through assessment of work done predictions that the suction surface region downstream of the shock, and the shock itself are key drivers for stability.

Phase plots of the unsteady gas pressure relative to the blade vibration are assessed and show that a qualitative difference in the pressure phase exists between aerofoil sections that have positive and negative aerodamping. The qualitative difference is shown to be due to the effect of separation on the suction surface affecting the group phase of upstream and downstream travelling unsteady pressure waves.

CW	Clockwise
dt	delta time
F	Frequency
IBPA	Inter Blade Phase Angle
LE	Leading Edge
ND	Nodal Diameter
NIV	Non-Integral Vibration
p	Pressure
PS	Pressure Surface
RANS	Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes
R_f	Reduced Frequency
SA	Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model
SS	Suction Surface
TE	Trailing Edge
URANS	Unsteady RANS
u, v, w	Cartesian velocity components
W	Work done
x, y, z	Cartesian spatial coordinates
x/C	Aerofoil distance / aerofoil chord length

Keywords: Aeroelasticity, Unsteady Aerodynamics, flutter

NOMENCLATURE

λ	Wavelength
$\bar{\phi}, \phi'$	Mean and fluctuating components
ω	Frequency
1F	1 st Flap mode
2ND	2 nd Nodal Diameter
ANX	X-directional cell face area
c	Speed of sound
C	Chord length
CCW	Counterclockwise
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics

1. INTRODUCTION

Flutter has been a known issue in aviation since at least 1916 when asymmetric vibrations were observed on the tail plane of a Hanley Page O/400 bomber [1]. An understanding of isolated aerofoil flutter near stall was proposed as early as 1928 [2] such that if the excitation force oscillates with a 90° phase shift from displacement, the body will flutter. This theory implied a pseudo-steady aerodynamic loading so that as an aerofoil vibrates, its aerodynamic load oscillates along the lift curve as the angle of attack changes. When non-integral vibrations were then seen in axial compressors at a high working line, an effort was made to apply this understanding (reviewed in [3]), which initiated the theory of how twist in the 1F modeshape provides a sufficient pitching moment to initiate the pitch-plunge coupling seen in isolated aerofoils. It has since been realised the complexity of

turbomachinery stall flutter is far more complicated than that for isolated aerofoils.

At least four physical mechanisms of an installed fan set interact during a 1F stall flutter event: blade modeshape, unsteady aerodynamics, inter-blade phase angle (IBPA), and duct acoustics. Of particular interest to this work is the 2nd mechanism: how is the unsteady aerodynamic behaviour of wide chord fan blades able to damp vibratory responses at one operating condition and yet excite the blade at another. Early attempts to understand this behaviour looked towards how unsteady aerodynamics could produce a harmonic forcing near stall conditions and employed a Strouhal number type parameter termed Reduced frequency

$$R_f = \frac{C\omega}{v} . \quad (1)$$

The Strouhal number for bluff bodies in incompressible flows is known to provide a rough guide as to when periodic shedding is achieved. The jump made here to installed fan flutter (as discussed in [4]), is that this type of non dimensional parameter can be used to indicate to what extent disturbances in the separated wake can interact with the flow over the blade surface.

Work done in [5] and [6] looked at the aerodynamic characteristics of a wide chord fan blade around a flutter stability point at a constant speed and compared flow features on the suction surface against radial distributions of work done. The papers describe how radial flow migration brought about by separation at a lower radial position correlated to negative damping at higher heights. [5] also finds correlations between flow separation and the phase of unsteady pressure over the suction surface. However, these works focus on a single blade and so it is difficult to understand whether radial flow migration is a common driver for flutter across all blades, or why indeed the unsteady pressure phase is affected by the radial flow migration.

The work in [7] showed how intake acoustics affected flutter stability and in particular, how the phase of a reflected acoustic wave from the intake entrance can significantly increase or decrease flutter stability. This finding lends support to the idea that the root cause of flutter is embedded within acoustics; that properties such as unsteady blade aerodynamics and blade modeshapes all affect flutter stability through how they influence local acoustic behaviour.

The investigations in [5], [6], [8], and [9] largely disagreed with the pseudo-steady view of excitation from blade vibrations and identified that unsteady shock oscillation is the primary driver for stall flutter on rig blades and not the stall itself. Suggesting unsteady pressure and interaction with shock strength and position were key variables to driving stall flutter. However, for the case of [8] and [9], it is unclear if the relatively small area at the shock foot driving work into the blade is sufficiently large to

overcome positive damping over the rest of the aerofoil, and whether this mechanism holds for a full scale blade.

This paper expounds the findings of a numerical investigation into 1F transonic fan flutter on full scale blades performed on a range of wide-chord transonic fan blades at a range of operating conditions, attempting to identify the root cause of how unsteady aerodynamics drives work into a fan blade near stall.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The investigation presented here is interested in understanding the effect of one particular component in its contribution to flutter stability, and so the numerical methodology outline below seeks to strip out the influence of as many of the other components as possible.

A total of 9 wide chord fan designs were used in this study across several operating points, accounting for the effects of steady untwist from centrifugal and aerodynamic loads. The blades covered a range of full scale and rig scale designs. CFD predictions are performed using AU3D; a finite-volume compressible flow solver applied to the 3D unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) equations [10] and validated for these predictions in [11]. Turbulence modelling was provided by a modified Spalart–Allmaras (SA) one-equation model, and all simulations were run using wall functions to treat the boundary layer. It was recognized early on in the work that flutter and its prediction is a multi-faceted problem, thus the challenge in this study was to find ways to simplify the modelling and physics capture so that the effect of interest could be isolated. Single passage flutter predictions were performed using phase lag boundary conditions [12] in order to isolate the ND of interest. The Figure 1 provides a schematic of the solution domain. Tip clearances and blade shapes are calculated and accurately represented in the meshed geometry.

Single passage, single bladerow fan domains typically use ~1M mesh nodes, and resolve LE, TE blade geometry as well as near wall and tip regions.

Figure 1: Illustration of the numerical domain

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Analysis of work done

In order to investigate 1F NIV stability, we will begin by first understanding what parts of the blade drive stability and what parts drive instability. Unsteady flutter calculations were performed and time dependent contours of blade surface pressure and displacement were recorded. This allows for the calculation of the work done for each mesh node i on the blade surface using

$$W_i = \int_0^T p_i (ANX_i u_i + ANY_i v_i + ANZ_i w_i) . dt , \quad (2)$$

where directional cell face areas (ANX, ANY, and ANZ) are multiplied by directional surface velocities (u_i , v_i and w_i) and static pressure p_i over a vibration cycle of time T . This then provides a direct connection between stability at

a node and the unsteady pressure acting on the blade surface at that node. Unsteady pressure of course can be characterised as a deviation from the mean pressure following

$$p_i = \bar{p} + p' , \quad (3)$$

where \bar{p} is the time and area averaged pressure and p' is the time varying area averaged pressure. In these predictions, the blade is made to oscillate harmonically at a fixed amplitude and so the pressure fluctuations are harmonic (at the 1F mode frequency) with an amplitude A and a phase ϕ relative to the blade displacement. All phase lag calculations in this work are performed with only the 2ND frequency preserved at the phase lag boundaries.

Figure 4: Work distributions for stable (left) and unstable (right) blade sections

Considering the large number of blade designs and operating points employed in this study, a systematic

approach was sought to quantify regions of the blade that were particularly influential to flutter stability. Hence pre-

defined spans (70, 75, 80, 85, and 90% span) were analysed giving a population of 425 aerofoils. Each aerofoil was then discretised so that the contribution to stability from each region on an aerofoil could be tracked – see Figure 2.

With this, the contribution to stability of each blade section region could be calculated and compared between a stable and unstable blade section. A bar graph plot of work distributions for a range of blade sections at a range of operating conditions is provided in Figure 4. Sections that have a total summed positive damping are plotted on the left in the stable chart and those with summed negative damping values are plotted on the right in the unstable chart.

Figure 2: Discretisation of an aerofoil

The work done bars are plotted against blade section region, and each series in a chart represents a blade section. 5 regions are plotted: pre-shock; shock + post shock; suction surface total; pressure surface total; and aerofoil total. The LE and TE regions were ignored as they were found to have a negligible influence on stability. It should be noted – using Figure 2 as a guide – that:

1. Aerofoil total = 2 + 3 + 4 + 5
2. SS total = 2 + 3 + 4
3. PS total = 5
4. Shock + post-shock = 3 + 4

Furthermore, within each chart, each colour (series) represents a blade section, hence the reader can trace the work distribution of different parts of a blade section by following its colour in each region. For a 2ND response, the pressure surface has been found to be mostly negative (destabilising), as shown in Figure 4, weakly positive only for a few cases that were studied. The pre-shock bars however, always seem to be positive (stabilising), hence in regions of the aerofoil where fluid packets have not yet encountered the presence of a discontinuity, there is a clear and consistent distinction between the work contributions of the suction and pressure surfaces. Some of the operating points plotted will be at the sea-level static working line, and others will be near stall. For the cases that are in 1F NIV regions, this provides a further important corollary; which is that the change in angle of attack and operating conditions of the blade does not change the sign of the work done by the pre-shock and pressure surface region of an aerofoil.

It can also be observed from this Figure 4, that although the pre-shock SS region is always positive, the SS total is not. There is a large amount of variability in the

SS total bars of unstable blade sections, and this suggests that aerofoil stability is driven by changes in excitation on the suction surface. On observation of the left (stable) chart, it is clear that stability depends on the suction surface being able to counteract the negative work done of the pressure surface. It does this by either having a:

1. highly damped pre-shock surface (box 1 in Fig. 4)
- or
2. highly damped shock + post-shock region (see box 2 in Fig. 4).

Cases with these features were looked at more closely and it was found that where there was a high pre-shock damping, these aerofoils typically had a more swallowed shock – indicative of being on a low working line away from stall flutter, thus these aerofoils are stable because of operating condition and not just design. The swallowed shock gives more space to a pre-shock region so increasing the area of positive damping on the suction surface. Cases where the damping of the shock + post-shock region was strongly positive or negative were found to be of interest in differentiating between why some blades have 1F NIV and why some don't on a high working line. Understanding the cause of this is the focus of the next section.

A study was then performed to understand how blade-to-blade aerodynamic coupling affects the work distribution over an aerofoil. For this, a case which presented with -ve damping for 2ND was run for all possible NDs (from -12 to +12) – see Figure 5. The results here show that the work contribution varies harmonically for each section of the aerofoil but with different magnitudes, and that the minimum total damping is reached when the suction surface contribution reaches a negative minimum. For NDs where the PS becomes -ve, the suction surface is able to compensate for NDs above +2 and keeps them stable. The pressure surface does not have a symmetric sinusoidal trend with ND, and appears to be responsible for the skewness typically seen in damping vs ND curves, and also suggests that multiple harmonics influence blade to blade stability through the pressure surface. The suction surface shows very slight levels of asymmetry and suggests that instability dominates when the IBPA is low and blades vibrate in unison. In corollary, the influence of neighbouring blades produces a stabilising effect as the IBPA increases. These damping correlations against ND are likely to vary considerably depending on blade design as well as other variables, but are not the basis of the present study.

Figure 5: Study of work done for different NDs, which go from -12 to +12 from left to right for each section.

4.3 Modelling of suction surface pressure waves

To understand why the work done for some aerofoils in the shock + post-shock region is positive and why for others it's negative, the phase of excitation must be studied. Figure 6 presents polar plots of the unsteady static pressure phase relative to blade motion, that have been grouped by whether the summed work done on the suction surface is positive or negative. The radial direction in these plots is x/C (normalised position along the blade chord), and phases are only plotted for the post-shock region. Hence the plot lines start at a non-zero radial position and travel outwards until reaching $x/C = 0.95$, which defines the start of the trailing edge region (as discretised in Figure 2). As per the forced 1DOF analogy, work done on the aerofoil is highest (most destabilising) when the phase is at $+90^\circ$ to the displacement and at its lowest (most stabilising) at -90° ($=270^\circ$).

Immediately, a clear qualitative difference can be observed in Figure 6 between aerofoils that have a stable or unstable suction surface (SS): For stable SS's, plot lines travel in a tight clockwise pattern around the polar plot and migrate through the $0-180^\circ$ phase region quickly; for unstable SS's, the phase starts in the same manner as the stable plot, but soon changes direction so more of the blade sits in the $0-180^\circ$ region of the plot. The direction of the turn in phase is important, when the phase plot has a clockwise trend, it indicates the phase is consistently decreasing over the post-shock region of the blade – an indication of a forward (downstream) travelling pressure wave; whereas a counter clock-wise phase plot indicates an increasing phase with position and hence a backward (upstream) travelling pressure wave. In the majority of unstable cases, the phase changes direction, travelling in a counter clock-wise manner to the bottom of the plot. The increased chord length spent in the top half of the plot – the negative work region – reduces the aerofoil's resistance to the negative work input from the PS, making it unstable.

Figure 6: Polar phase plots of pressure relative to aerofoil displacement. Radial axis is x/C from shock to TE

Of course, the amplitude of the pressure must also be considered here, and this is provided in Figure 7 and shows no significant difference in pressure amplitude between stable and unstable SS. However, it is interesting to note that the amplitude tends to decrease along the length of the blade from the region near the shock (which tends to have a $+90^\circ$ phase and hence produces negative work) to the TE (which tends to have a $+270^\circ$ phase and positive work). So in addition to the work done balance between the SS and the PS. A further work done balance exists between the pre-shock and near-shock vs the post-shock regions of the SS. A post-shock region that is too negative here, destabilises the SS, which then drives the

stability of the whole aerofoil. Interestingly, many of the amplitudes for unstable SS' show a drop in amplitude between $x/C=0.9$ to 0.95 , before the amplitude recovers to levels seen at $x/C=0.8$. This is not seen in the stable plot, which instead shows a less severe but gradual and consistent reduction. Potential reasons behind this are discussed later on in this paper. Hence in order to understand what drives an aerofoil's stability, the phase of the pressure waves downstream of the shock must be understood, and particularly, what causes them to travel upstream or downstream, so producing clockwise or counter clock-wise phase profiles in Figure 6. In order to do this, attempts were made to model the phase change seen in Figure 6 numerically. The first step was to try and model the nominal clockwise phase profile. Some clockwise phase profiles have been re-plotted with cartesian co-ordinates in Figure 8 to show the typical magnitude of phase change ($\approx 220^\circ$) that occurs in the post-shock region.

Figure 7: Unsteady pressure amplitude in the post-shock region

This 220° change occurs for some aerofoils over a spatial distance as small as 20cm. Using values from an example blade and its CFD predictions, a simple wavelength calculation is presented here:

$$c = f\lambda, \tag{4}$$

$$f = 140\text{Hz} \text{ , (flutter frequency)} \tag{5}$$

$$\text{Near wall parallel velocity} \sim 150\text{ms}^{-1}, \tag{6}$$

$$c \sim 350\text{ms}^{-1}, \tag{7}$$

$$\lambda_{\text{forward}} = \frac{350+150}{140} \approx 3.6\text{m}, \tag{8}$$

Figure 8: Forward travelling pressure wave phase distributions

which over a distance of 20cm gives a phase change of only $360 \times 0.2/3.6 = 20^\circ$, and is significantly lower than that predicted by CFD. From this, it is clear that for the phase difference to be acoustically driven, there must be more than 1 acoustic wave. A model was then produced to consider whether two overlapping acoustic waves could produce a group velocity and hence a group phase change of 220° . One wave was modelled as travelling from the shock to the trailing edge and another going in the reverse direction from the trailing edge to the shock – illustrated in Figure 9. The amplitude of the waves are assumed to be the same, and are not modelled to decay over the distance. The source of the upstream travelling wave will be discussed later in this section, but for now it can be presumed to either be emitted from the wake at the TE or from the shock (and travels downstream to the TE before being reflected back). This type of model was used to predict the group phase for a range of phase differences between the downstream and upstream travelling waves – this is plotted in Figure 10. It can be seen here that depending on the phase difference of the two acoustic waves, the phase can change over the post-shock region of the blade by $\sim 180^\circ$. This is a significant improvement over the 20° estimated for a single acoustic wave and gives some support to the idea that the pressure phase variation is driven by acoustic waves.

Figure 9: Illustration of modelling two acoustic wave grouping

Figure 10: Plot of group phase from two acoustic waves in cartesian (top) and polar (bottom) axes

However, there still exists a range of $\sim 40^\circ$ that is unaccounted for in the acoustic model, and the qualitative trend of the clock-wise phase lines in Figure 6 are different to those observed from CFD. Noticeably, some of the phase lines in Figure 6 appear to change the rate at which phase decreases in different regions of the blade – the purple lines that kink upwards at $\sim 0.6 x/C$. The relatively abrupt change in direction could possibly be due to a change in propagation speed of the group wave, and so the velocity contours from steady state CFD runs were plotted – Figure 11 – with a cartoon aerofoil superimposed. Tracing the flow path from the LE to TE, the flow accelerates around the LE where some clustering can be seen. From here velocity remains relatively stable until the shock, where further clustering can be seen. As the pressure recovers and flow accelerates, close the wall, the velocity again remains relatively stable. This is until $\sim 0.8 x/C$ where it begins to decelerate. Here, on the approach to the TE, clustering increases and up to 4 isolines are crossed. A simplistic representation of the flow deceleration was applied to the acoustic model (Figure 12) to produce the phase plot in Figure 13 (top). To show how well a very simple model such as this compares against the CFD phase contours of Figure 6, the envelope of the plot lines from the model are superimposed over the clockwise plots from CFD.

This comparison shows that the phase profile from CFD can be reproduced with at least two acoustic waves over a non-homogeneous velocity field. Different phases of the acoustic waves, and the amount of variation in flow velocity produce different magnitudes of phase change, but the qualitative trend of the phase plots is always the same.

Figure 11: Isovelocity lines of a blade section, with contours 20 m/s apart

With this understanding in place, the question then turns to why for the unstable SS profiles the phase profile has a qualitatively different trend. To understand this, various aspects of the acoustic model were interrogated and ultimately it was found that a reduction in amplitude of

the upstream travelling acoustic wave at about $0.6 - 0.8x/C$ can produce a change in direction of the phase lines. So the upstream wave amplitude was modelled to decay using the profile in Figure 14, whilst the amplitude of the downstream wave was fixed to 1 along the entire

distance. With this modification, the phase lines are seen to change direction as shown in Figure 15 (top). The key feature being that the upstream wave amplitude starts slightly higher than that of the downstream one at $x = 0.15\text{m}$, and decays whilst the downstream wave maintains a constant amplitude of 1.0. This produces the effect of the combined group wave having a phase that is travelling downstream up to $x/C \approx 0.5$ before transitioning to an upstream travelling wave beyond that.

Figure 12: Velocity profile applied to two wave acoustic model

Figure 15 shows phase relatively unchanged (although having a CW curl) during the first half of the chord before sweeping in a CCW manner as it approaches the TE. As before, the envelope of these phase lines have been superimposed on top of the CFD predicted ones in Figure 15 (bottom), and shows a very good match between the two.

Whilst it is relatively simple to identify what features of a model can produce a desired pattern, it is challenging to understand why. In this scenario, why would an upstream travelling wave from the TE decay in amplitude over such a short distance but not the downstream wave. For acoustic waves in ducts, cut-on and cut-off frequencies play an important role to define whether the reflected acoustic wave amplitude will have an effect on stability [7]. When applying a similar logic to this problem, inferring the blade-to-blade passage to be a duct, the high velocity gradients close to the wall (particularly of interest here) add complexity. Here the work done on acoustic waves in boundary layers [13] and shear flows [14] was instead found to be particularly enlightening. [14] considers the effect of a shear flow on acoustic waves using the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations – deriving equation (9). Although it's for a different regime to the transonic fan blade flows considered here, equation (9) still provides insights into understanding acoustic propagation behaviour in non-uniform carrier flows.

$$\frac{d^2 p'}{dt^2} - \bar{c}^2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 p'}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 p'}{\partial y^2} \right) = \frac{d\bar{u}_x}{dy} \left(2\bar{\rho} \frac{\partial u'_y}{\partial x} + \bar{u}_y \frac{\partial \rho'}{\partial x} \right) \quad (9)$$

Figure 13: Phase plots of acoustics model for a range of phase differences between the upstream and downstream wave (top), and the envelope of these plot lines superimposed in black over CFD lines (bottom)

The LHS of equation (9) is the acoustic wave equation and the RHS can be considered as a description of inhomogeneities in the fluid field that affect the acoustic acceleration. So for a wave travelling downstream with the flow, $\frac{d\bar{u}_x}{dy}$ is positive and so the shear flow terms on the RHS of equation (9) act to reduce the acceleration of unsteady pressure. For a Blasius type boundary layer profile, this effect is stronger closer to the wall, hence causing the acoustic intensity of a downstream wave to increase closer to the wall. For an upstream travelling wave, the mean flow velocity and its gradient $\left(\frac{d\bar{u}_x}{dy}\right)$ are negative so accelerating the unsteady pressure waves and decreasing acoustic

intensity. This has the effect for reducing acoustic intensity closer to the wall for a boundary layer type profile.

Figure 14: upstream wave amplitude profile

Figure 15: Acoustic model of CCW phase lines (top) and comparison against CFD phase calculations (bottom)

Whilst this process is considered to affect both stable and unstable aerofoils, it is asserted here that the effect is significantly more pronounced for blades that are in the process of stalling by separation in this region. This would then lead to a step change in behaviour, a significant phase change and also potentially the amplitude trend discussed for Figure 7.

4. CONCLUSION

The paper presents an investigation into the root cause of stall flutter on wide chord transonic fan blades. It identifies that the suction surface region of the shock and downstream of the shock is particularly influential in defining stability of an aerofoil. The group phase of the unsteady static pressure relative to blade motion is found to qualitatively change in this region between well stable and unstable aerofoils. This is explained by separation near the trailing edge that affects the propagation of upstream and downstream travelling acoustic waves, which in turn defines the group phase and ultimately determines stability.

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